

NUMERICAL EVALUATION OF SHEAR STRENGTH ENHANCEMENT IN RC BEAMS INCORPORATING VARIOUS WEB OPENING CONFIGURATIONS AND PRE-STRESSED FE-SMA BAR SIZES

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Abstract. Web openings in reinforced concrete (RC) beams are commonly required to accommodate utility ducts, pipes, and other service installations, optimizing space utilization and reducing construction costs. However, these openings can severely compromise the structural integrity of beams, mainly by lowering their shear strength, thus necessitating innovative reinforcement techniques to maintain their load-bearing capacity. This study presents a numerical investigation to enhance the shear strength of RC beams with various web opening shapes by integrating pre-stressed Fe-SMA (Iron-based Shape Memory Alloy) bars. The analysis focuses on two key parameters: the shape of the web openings and the diameter of the Fe-SMA bars. Finite element modeling was used to simulate RC beams with rectangular, circular, and diamond-shaped openings, and the impact of different Fe-SMA bar sizes on shear capacity was systematically evaluated. The results demonstrated that the incorporation of pre-stressed Fe-SMA bars significantly enhances the shear strength of RC beams, with the extent of improvement closely tied to both the geometry of the openings and the bar diameter. Under four-point loading, beams with diamond and circular openings exhibited fewer diagonal cracks and greater shear strength than those with square openings, especially when reinforced with larger Fe-SMA bars. Compared to the control beam (without opening), beams with diamond-shaped openings strengthened with 32 mm Fe-SMA bars showed the closest performance with only a 2% reduction in load capacity. In contrast, circular and square-shaped openings resulted in load reductions of 9.4% and 25.6%, respectively. These findings suggest that optimizing both the size of Fe-SMA bars and the shape of web openings is an effective strategy for enhancing the structural performance of RC beams with web openings.

Keywords: RC beams; FE-SMA; Web opening; Pre-stressed; Numerical; Shear strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Web openings in reinforced concrete (RC) beams are commonly adopted to permit the passage of electrical and mechanical utilities such as pipes and ducts. The presence of web openings in beams eliminates the need for dropped ceilings, which results in an overall decrease in the building's weight and height [1]. This leads to a more efficient and cost-effective design. However, web openings cause significant losses in beams' flexural and shear capacities because they disrupt the flow of stresses, causing stress concentrations around openings. The influence of openings in the flexural and shear zones on beams has been investigated in numerous studies [2], [3]. Web openings in the shear zones can have various sizes and shapes depending on their purpose of use [4]. Shear forces cause diagonal tensile stresses in the shear zone of RC beams [5]. These forces are resisted by concrete struts acting in compression and shear reinforcement acting in tension [6]. Introducing openings in the shear zone reduces the amount of concrete, which results in insufficient strength to resist shear forces. Openings result in high stress concentrations around openings, with the opening shape and size influencing the amount of stress

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concentration [7]. Stress concentrations around openings cause significant reductions in the ultimate strength, shear capacity, and rigidity of beams [8].

Studies reported that openings in the shear zone diminish the load-carrying capacity of RC beams more than openings in the flexure zone [9]–[12]. Introducing openings near the supports changes the beam behavior from shear-controlled to flexure-controlled due to insufficient material in the diagonal compression strut [13]. This leads to premature failures, such as web compression failure. Alsheikh et al. [11] investigated the influence of opening locations on the load-carrying capacity of beams. Results showed that circular openings located at the midspan reduce the load-carrying capacity by 5%, while openings near the supports cause a significant reduction of around 25%. Another study by Jasim et al. [14] found that openings near the supports reduce the ultimate load capacity and torque by 45% and 43.8%, compared to openings located in the midspan. Openings in near supports interrupt the interaction between moment and shear, substantially reducing the load-carrying capacity. The closer the openings to supports, the higher the impact on moment and shear [15], [16].

The structural behavior of beams with openings is influenced by the shear span-to-depth ratio, opening size and location, and tension reinforcement ratio [9]. Beams can preserve their elastic and plastic deformations if the opening size is small. Ame et al. [17] reported that circular openings with a diameter less than 40% of the beam effective depth do not significantly influence ultimate load capacity or first cracking. Another study by Mwonga et al. [7] examined the influence of square opening sizes on the behavior of beams. Results showed square openings exceeding 25% of the overall beam depth cause significant deflections and cracking. This indicates that square openings cause higher stress concentrations than circular openings, especially at the corners.

Reinforcing beam openings is necessary to prevent premature failures. Many researchers explored various materials and techniques to strengthen openings. Fiber-reinforced polymers (FRP) and shape memory alloys (SMA) are commonly used to strengthen openings due to their remarkable characteristics. Rahim et al. [18] investigated the effectiveness of carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) sheets in strengthening beam openings in the shear zone. Results showed that the thickness of CFRP sheets needed to strengthen openings mainly depends on the beam-to-depth ratio. The effective number of CFRP layers for deep beams having opening diameters of 150 mm and 200 mm was found to be two and three, respectively [18]. Elkafrawy et al. [19] examined the effectiveness of iron shape memory alloys (Fe-SMA) in reinforcing beam openings in the shear zone. Fe-SMA bars around openings allowed openings to regain their shear capacity and behave similarly to beams without openings. This is due to the ability of Fe-SMA to recover strains upon heating and unloading [20]. Pre-stressing Fe-SMA is considered an effective method for enhancing the overall behavior of beams with openings. This method can reduce stress concentration and fracture localization. Prestressing Fe-SMA bars by 30% and 60% enhanced beams' load capacity, with 100 mm x 150 mm openings by 12% and 9%, respectively [19].

Although numerous studies have explored the behavior of beams with openings, limited research has focused explicitly on strengthening these openings with Fe-SMA bars. This gap highlights the need for further investigation into the potential benefits of Fe-SMA bars for enhancing the structural performance of such beams. Thus, this study uses ABAQUS simulations to numerically evaluate the performance of beams with various opening shapes, including square, circular, and diamond. Under a four-point loading scheme, the behavior of beams with these opening shapes will be assessed and compared to solid beams, thoroughly examining the effectiveness of Fe-SMA bar reinforcement in strengthening the web openings.

2 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

2.1 Material constitutive models

Three-dimensional (3D) finite element (FE) models of RC beams with different shaped openings and strengthened using Fe-SMA bars of various diameters are modeled using ABAQUS. The Fe-SMA bars are characterized by an elastic modulus of 133 GPa and a Poisson's ratio of 0.3. This FE analysis aims to thoroughly understand the structural performance of the studied RC beams under load without the need for experimental tests. The modeling of the Fe-SMA bars in ABAQUS is performed based on the simulation parameters outlined in earlier research [20]. Generally, the behavior of concrete in structural elements is represented in ABAQUS through various models. The smeared cracking model assumes consistent concrete behavior without considering cracks at high loads, while the brittle cracking model examines cracks under low strains. On the other hand, the concrete damaged plasticity (CDP) model combines aspects of both smeared and brittle cracking models to provide a comprehensive representation of concrete behavior and damage under tension and compression [21]. This allows

the CDP model to account for material plasticity and crack propagation. As a result, this study utilized the CDP model for concrete in RC beams. The constitutive models employed have been thoroughly detailed in the author's prior research [19].

2.2 Element types

This study employed a 20 mm element mesh size to get accurate results while minimizing computational time. The behavior of steel and Fe-SMA reinforcement bars is represented by a 2-node linear 3D truss element. For optimal bonding, the embedded rebar is surrounded by concrete [20], [22] represented by an 8-node linear brick solid element with reduced integration. This approach creates a balance between accuracy and computational efficiency through reduced integrations.

2.2 Specimens configuration

The study investigates RC beams 450 mm deep and 200 mm wide, with a shear span of 1000 mm and a loaded length of 2800 mm, under four-point loading. Figure 1 displays the beams' geometry and reinforcement details. Figure 1a illustrates the control beam without openings, whose structural behavior is compared to beams with openings. RC beams with three different web opening shapes: circular, square, and diamond, are presented in Figures 1b, 1c, and 1d, respectively. Figure 2 depicts the cross-sectional of the beam. All openings are 200 mm × 200 mm, but the diameter of the Fe-SMA reinforcing bars varies among the samples. Table 1 presents the test specimen details.

Figure 1: Specimen geometry with different web opening shapes: (a) B-Control; (b) B-Circle-2T18; (c) B-Square-2T18; (d) B-Diamond-2T18.

Figure 2: Cross-sectional view of the beam.

Table 1: Specimen Details

Group	Opening shape	Beam ID	Opening dimensions	Reinforcement		
				Type	Diameter (mm)	
Control	-	B-Control	-	-	-	
		B-Circle-10				10
		B-Circle-18				18
Group I	Circle	B-Circle-32	200 × 200	Fe-SMA	32	
		B-Square-10			10	
		B-Square-18			18	
Group II	Square	B-Square-32	200 × 200	Fe-SMA	32	
		B-Diamond-10			10	
		B-Diamond-18			18	
Group III	Diamond	B-Diamond-32	200 × 200	Fe-SMA	32	

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Modeling verification

For reliable results, the FEM model is verified through experimental work. This verification is essential to ensure that the model accurately replicates the behavior of RC beams under four-point loading. The verification has been done by comparing the results obtained from the FEM analysis with the experimental data published by Shahverdi et al. [22]. Although there are minor inconsistencies between the load vs. deflection curves derived from the experimental data with those produced from the FEM analysis, there is still a strong correlation between the results. The variations are due to limitations and assumptions in numerical modeling. The validation results have been previously presented in the authors' earlier work [23].

3.2 Cracking pattern

The opening shape and the size of the Fe-SMA reinforcing bars primarily influence the cracking pattern of beams with openings. As shown in Figure 3, beams with circular, square, and diamond-shaped openings exhibit different crack propagation behaviors. In the control beam (B-Control), which has no openings, cracking is concentrated near the center, with the maximum damage occurring at the midspan. In contrast, beams with openings display distinct cracking patterns based on the shape of the opening and the size of the reinforcing bars. Circular and diamond-shaped openings experience fewer diagonal cracks than square openings, regardless of the reinforcement size. This is because circular and diamond openings distribute stress more evenly due to their geometric properties. In contrast, square openings create stress concentrations at their sharp corners, which weakens the beam and leads to premature failure.

The size of the Fe-SMA bars also significantly impacts stress concentration around the openings. Beams with larger reinforcement bar diameters, such as B-Circle-32, B-Square-32, and B-Diamond-32, demonstrate reduced cracking and stress distribution closely resembling the control beam, indicating that the larger bars provide better reinforcement. This reduces the adverse effects of openings by spreading the stress more evenly across the beam. Conversely, beams with smaller reinforcement diameters, like B-Circle-10, B-Square-10, and B-Diamond-10, show higher stress concentrations and more pronounced cracking around the openings, especially in areas close to the edges. This underscores the necessity of using adequate reinforcement in beams with openings to avoid stress accumulation, which can compromise the structural integrity. Therefore, increasing the reinforcement bar diameter effectively enhances the beam's capacity to manage stress around critical areas like openings, improving overall structural performance.

Figure 3: Cracking patterns of beams.

3.3 Effect of opening shape

The load-deflection behavior of reinforced concrete beams with various web opening shapes, as depicted in Figure 4, demonstrates a clear impact of opening geometry on both the load-carrying capacity and deflection characteristics throughout the loading stages. These stages consist of an initial elastic phase, a cracking phase, a peak load point, and a post-peak softening phase. During the elastic phase, all beams, including those with openings, behave similarly to the control beam until initial cracking begins. The cracking phase is marked by the development of both flexural and shear cracks, during which beams with larger reinforcement bars, especially in the diamond-shaped openings, maintain better performance. Diamond openings demonstrate the highest shear capacity at the peak load, closely followed by circular openings, while square openings lag behind. In the post-peak softening phase, beams with diamond and circular openings display more gradual reductions in stiffness, reflecting better crack control and ductility, whereas square openings exhibit rapid stiffness loss.

The control beam without openings (B-Control) sets the highest benchmark with a peak load of 540 kN. Beams with diamond-shaped openings exhibit the highest load-carrying capacity among the beams with openings. For instance, the beam reinforced with 32 mm Fe-SMA bars (B-Diamond-32) achieved a peak load of 529 kN, which is only 2% lower than the control beam. Notably, the diamond-shaped opening outperforms other shapes, surpassing the circular-shaped beam (B-Circle-32), which reached a maximum load of 489 kN, about 8.2% lower than B-Diamond-32 and 9.4% lower than the control. Diamond openings also gradually soften after the peak, indicating better stiffness retention and crack control than other shapes. The most pronounced negative effect is seen in beams with square-shaped openings. For example, the beam with 32 mm Fe-SMA bars (B-Square-32) only achieved a peak load of 402 kN, marking a 25.6% reduction from the control and a 24.0% reduction compared to the B-Diamond-32 beam. This significant drop in capacity is accompanied by a steeper decline in stiffness after the peak load, indicating poorer crack resistance and overall reduced structural integrity.

Beams with openings experienced lower energy absorption capacities than the control beam. This is due to the accumulation of stresses around the openings, which reduces the beam's strength and energy absorption capacity [24]-[28]. Nevertheless, among beams with openings, the superior performance of the diamond-shaped openings can be attributed to their geometry, which allows for better stress distribution and crack control around the openings. This reduces stress concentration compared to square openings, which are more susceptible to sharp corners where cracks can initiate. Circular openings also perform well, but their curved edges, while smooth, seem to concentrate less shear resistance compared to diamond shapes. The square-shaped openings' sharp corners cause more pronounced stress concentrations and reduced load-bearing performance, which justifies their lower overall capacity and stiffness.

Figure 4: Effect of opening shape on the load-deflection response for beams with different Fe-SMA bar sizes.

3.4 Effect of Fe-SMA bar size

The load-deflection behavior shown in Figure 5 illustrates the impact of different Fe-SMA bar sizes on beams with varying opening shapes, specifically circular, square, and diamond-shaped openings. The overall trend indicates that increasing the Fe-SMA bar diameter enhances the load-carrying capacity and stiffness retention of the beams, though the extent of improvement varies based on the shape of the opening. For beams with circular-shaped openings (Figure 5a), the increase in Fe-SMA bar size significantly improves ultimate load. The beam reinforced with 32 mm bars (B-Circle-32) achieves a peak load of 489 kN, while those reinforced with 18 mm (B-Circle-18) and 10 mm (B-Circle-10) Fe-SMA bars reach peak loads of 484 kN and 432 kN, respectively. This shows that increasing the bar size from 10 mm to 32 mm leads to a 13.2% improvement in ultimate load. The larger bars also lead to better post-peak stiffness retention, as evidenced by the more gradual reduction in load after the peak, compared to the more drastic drop in smaller bars.

Similarly, the ultimate load increases with Fe-SMA bar size for beams with square-shaped openings (Figure 5b). The beam with 32 mm bars (B-Square-32) reaches a peak load of 402 kN, followed by 397 kN for the 18 mm bars (B-Square-18) and 349 kN for the 10 mm bars (B-Square-10). The increase from 10 mm to 32 mm bars results in a 15.2% improvement in ultimate load. However, even with the increase in bar size, square openings result in the lowest load-carrying capacity among the shapes, indicating that square openings concentrate stress more unfavorably compared to circular or diamond shapes. Moreover, the post-peak stiffness loss is more pronounced for square openings, particularly for the smaller bars, indicating that square openings are more sensitive to bar size reductions in terms of stiffness and ductility.

Beams with diamond-shaped openings (Figure 5c) demonstrate the highest ultimate load values. The beam reinforced with 32 mm bars (B-Diamond-2T32) achieves a peak load of 529 kN, very close to the control beam's 540 kN. The 18 mm (B-Diamond-2T18) and 10 mm (B-Diamond-2T10) versions achieve 526 kN and 468 kN, respectively. The improvement in load capacity from 10 mm to 32 mm bars is around 13%. Diamond-shaped

openings exhibit superior structural performance compared to circular and square openings, likely due to more efficient stress distribution and crack control around the opening. Additionally, the post-peak stiffness retention is superior in beams with larger bars, with diamond-shaped openings showing the least drastic reduction in stiffness compared to circular and square openings. Increasing the Fe-SMA bar size in all cases enhances the beams' load-bearing capacity by distributing the stress more effectively and controlling crack propagation. Larger bars (32 mm) demonstrate superior performance by allowing the beams to sustain higher loads before significant deflection occurs, leading to improved stiffness and ductility in the post-peak phase. Smaller bars (10 mm), while still enhancing the structural integrity of the beams, result in lower load capacities and a sharper decline in stiffness after peak loading, particularly in beams with square openings.

Figure 5: Effect of Fe-SMA bar size on the load-deflection response for beams with different opening shapes.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Openings in beams can significantly compromise their structural integrity and reduce their service life by concentrating stresses and promoting crack development. Reinforcing these openings with Fe-SMA bars is an effective technique that mitigates these adverse effects. This study examined the behavior of beams with various web-opening shapes in the shear zone by analyzing load-deflection relationships. A comparison was made between strengthened and unstrengthened beams with the following key conclusions:

- Beams with diamond and circular openings exhibited fewer diagonal cracks compared to beams with square openings. This is attributed to their geometric configurations, which allow for more even stress distribution, reducing stress concentrations that would otherwise accelerate crack formation in beams with square openings.
- Reinforcing beam openings with Fe-SMA bars significantly minimized stress localization and delayed crack development around the openings. This improvement is due to the unique properties of Fe-SMA bars, including the shape memory effect and superelasticity, which help to redistribute forces more effectively around the openings.
- Larger Fe-SMA bar diameters effectively prevented the early initiation of cracks around the openings. Increasing the bar diameter from 10 mm to 32 mm enhanced the load-carrying capacity of beams across all

opening shapes. For instance, beams with diamond-shaped openings reinforced with 18 mm and 32 mm Fe-SMA bars supported ultimate loads of 526 kN and 529 kN, respectively, which is comparable to the 540 kN capacity of the solid beam (without openings).

- Strengthening openings with 32 mm Fe-SMA bars resulted in the least reduction in ultimate load capacity for beams with diamond openings, showing only a 2% decrease compared to the control beam. In contrast, strengthening beams with square openings also increased their capacity. Still, it resulted in the most significant reduction, approximately 25.5%, in ultimate load capacity compared to beams with diamond and circular openings.

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